

ISSUES OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN SCHOOLS

Kurbanbaeva Mirigul Jenisbaevna

Student at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, English Language and Literature, Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742290>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 5-iyul 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 8-iyul 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 15-iyul 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

school, pedagogue-technologist, innovation, education, method, training, knowledge, skill.

ABSTRACT

In this article, innovative approaches to English language teaching in general education schools, students' free thinking, speaking depth, current responsibility, ways of improving the quality of education by the use of innovative methods by the English language teacher of general secondary schools are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the interest of the young generation in learning foreign languages, especially English, is increasing. Therefore, in order to teach this language more deeply in general education schools, pedagogues are required to make extensive use of innovative methods. The introduction of continuous teaching of foreign languages in the first grades of general education schools from 2013-2014 is a clear proof of this.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is known that nowadays in our country great attention is paid to learning foreign languages. The more attention we pay to the foundation of a building, the more solid it is and the more guaranteed it will serve you for hundreds of years. Our highest goal is to further strengthen the knowledge of foreign languages of the growing youth and the future of our country by ensuring the implementation of several decisions and orders of the head of state aimed at learning foreign languages. According to the final results of the republican stage of the competition "The best school for teaching foreign languages", Namangan (7th school, 1st place), Tashkent (145th school, 2nd place) and Bukhara (1st school, 3rd place) 3 schools in the regions won. 70 students and 14 teachers of these schools were sent to England. Learning a foreign language is very important for the next stage [in life] of each of our young people. That is, in order to raise the flag of Uzbekistan in the competitive, international arenas, it is very important to study the language in science, regardless of the direction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

English language teaching has experienced many changes and challenges since its formal inception as a separate field of education. Our current time is no exception and given the pandemic many issues now starkly confront English language institutions, schools and teachers. Those new to English language teaching might think the only issues are those about how to teach in class – methods. Which activities work best? Which approaches we should take? What makes a good curriculum (textbook or not) or teacher?

However, the field is a wide and deep one and consists of a lot more than just this one domain of classroom teaching. Currently, there are a lot of issues under debate which teachers need to form beliefs around – beliefs that will inform their teaching practices and educational philosophy. As part of the standards of practice for any teacher, being informed, aware and reflecting on the important issues and challenges in the profession as a whole is an essential part of all teacher education and development [3].

We aim in this paper to review the current issues facing the profession of English language teaching. It takes a critical stance on many of these issues, believing this is the proper perspective in which to assess the nature of change happening. More questions than answers will be offered but that's just part of assessing the future, a future we just never can 100% know with certainty.

Young children have a very high desire to learn a language, especially with today's information and communication tools. On the part of our state, the conditions created in schools, the classrooms equipped with modern technologies, the provision of young knowledgeable personnel, the organization of television online lessons on online TV channels for all classes for independent study outside of school lessons are commendable. When learning English, grammar rules are first explained to students and then reinforced through examples. This method is often useful for high school students. For example, tenses, prepositions, articles are well-known terms for high school students, they can make sentences by putting parts of sentences such as have, determiner, complement, and case in sentences. In grammar, two different methods are used effectively [4].

- Inductive
- Deductive

In the inductive method, grammar rules are first explained to students and then reinforced through examples. This method is often useful for high school students. For example, tenses, prepositions, articles are known terms for high school students. In the deductive method, the topic is first introduced through certain games and exercises, and then it is explained based on the rule. Since primary school students do not have knowledge about possessives, participles, verbs and other units, it is more effective to explain the topic to them through games and songs. Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in which a person undergoes complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method. All three methods are closely related and complement each other. Since the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during foreign language learning and the method of communicative didactics is created.

The application of methods in foreign language teaching has been around for a long time, and principles are relatively new methodological terms. Historically, the methods were grouped into four groups, and their names were called "translation", "correct", "comparative", "mixed". Learning foreign languages is not only a means of intellectual education, but it is a process of formation of a person's personality by getting to know the educational resources and values of a foreign culture and applying them to one's own cultural life. In Europe, the study of foreign languages has long been considered a privilege in higher education, and public schools are seen as educating the privileged few [5]. According to psychologists, compared to older people, children are 70-80% more interested in new things, reading and learning. Children try to perform tasks that they cannot perform even in our daily life despite warnings. They get

bored of the sameness very quickly, therefore, it is required from the teaching staff to organize classes in new ways, in an unconventional way, to fully create the environment of the foreign language being studied.

Today, many modern technologies and methods are entering the education system. However, in what way, at what time, and on what subject they are used, I think it depends on the teacher's ingenuity, inquisitiveness, and organizing the lessons in a way that is both interesting and rich in scientific information.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth noting that, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, English language in general education schools is taught to pedagogical innovative technologies that help to fully satisfy their interest and needs in learning a foreign language. Based on modern lesson developments, the lessons are highly effective for students to learn the language. As a result of the use of innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies. possible

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